

OSB PANEL WITH LOW DENSITY REFORESTING WOOD RESIDUE: PHYSICAL AND THERMAL CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This work aims to evaluate the potential use of low-density reforesting wood residues in OSB panel production made of an organic matrix with a focus on the physical characteristics of the panel. Physical and chemical characterization of the wood particles and thermo-physics (bulk density, density profile and thermal conductivity) properties of panels were carried out. Panels with a density of 550 kg/m³ and 13 % resin content were produced. The density profile showed uniform compaction throughout the thickness (ranging from 530.1 to 560.4 kg/m³) and the thermal conductivity test led to a 0.146 W/mK value, which allows the application of the composite as a thermal insulator.

KEYWORDS

oriented particles; wood waste; density profile; thermal properties; physical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Residual forest biomass (RFB) is composed of vegetable materials that come from silviculture processes, extractivism, wood transformation in sawmills, pulp and paper mills, board and plywood factories, and the furniture sector. The destiny of this waste is generally to be burned to produce electricity.

Several researchers have evaluated the application of fibrous raw material from agro-industrial by-products or forest biomass for making particleboard agglomerated with organic or inorganic resin in different regions of the world (Fiorelli et al., 2014, 2019; Nakanishi et al, 2018; Varanda et al., 2018). These studies indicate the possibility of obtaining engineered products with control of density as well as physical and mechanical properties, in addition to having better dimensional stability when compared to some species of sawn wood.

Brazil currently generates about 35 million cubic meters of RFB per year (Barbirato, 2018). OSB (Oriented Strand Board) panels are made of oriented, thin, and long wood particles (strands), consolidated using resin, heat, and pressure (Bortoletto Júnior & Garcia, 2004). They are formed by three layers of particles whereas the two external layers are parallel to each other and have a direction perpendicular to the middle layer (Tsoumis, 1991). It is a panel that requires lower quality wood in comparison to that needed for the production of plywood panels and combined with its mechanical properties competes in the market with plywood, which requires high-quality logs for its manufacture and is relatively more expensive (Bortoletto Júnior & Garcia, 2004).

In Brazil, most OSB is manufactured with the wood of the genus *Eucalyptus* and *Pinus* from reforesting areas and the exploitation of forest residues as raw material for the wood composites panel industry is quite limited and not expressive. In this context, this research aimed to evaluate the potential of low-density reforestation wood residues (LDWR) as a raw material for the production of OSB agglomerated with castor oil-based polyurethane resin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section shows the materials and methods used for the manufacture and characterization of OSB flat panels made of low-density reforesting wood residues.

Materials

To make the OSB-oriented strand board, low-density reforesting wood residues from disposal areas (SisGen A4206B8) was used. The resin used as a binder was the castor oil-based bicomponent polyurethane - type AGT1315 - composed of a polyol derived from castor oil and a petroleum prepolymer mixed in a 1:1 ratio with cold curing.

Methods

Characterization of low-density reforesting wood residues (LDWR)

The wood residues were collected and characterized regarding their physical and chemical properties following the methodology used by (Barbirato, 2018). Real density, bulk density (according to NBR7190, 1997), pH, and chemical analysis (aiming to verify the cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin contents of the residual biomass) tests were performed as a way to evaluate the potential of the material to be used as raw material in OSB oriented strand board.

Production of OSB from low-density reforestation wood residue (OSB-LDWR)

The residual wood went through a process of section uniformization and then strands were produced in a chipping mill (Marconi brand) generating particles with dimensions of approximately 9 cm long, 2.5 cm wide, and 0.1 cm thick. The strands were sieved and then dried in an oven at a temperature of 65 °C for 48 hours, according to Figure 1a. After the raw material preparation and drying phase, the resin was mixed with the wood through a spraying process using a rotary mixer (Figure 1b) and flat panels were shaped with a density of 550 kg/m³, 13 % of resin about the particle mass placed in a panel with dimensions 40 cm x 40 cm x 1 cm and particle mass distribution in a ratio of 30:40:30 % (face: core: face). The pressing was performed in a thermo-hydraulic press at a temperature of 100°C, for 10 min an average pressure of 3 MPa (Figure 1c). Figure 1d shows the formed OSB panel. After pressing, the panels were laid out at room temperature for 72 hours for the total curing of the resin.

Figure 1: Production steps for OSB-LDWR

Characterization of OSB-LDWR panels

Physical and thermal properties of OSB-MRBD panels were determined following the guidelines of the standards: Apparent Density (EN 323, 1993), Thermal Conductivity (ASTM E1530, 2011) and Density Profile (Bellini et al., 2009).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of LDWR

Table 1 shows the bulk density values and chemical composition of LDWR wood particles and other wood species used by the wood-based composite panel industry.

Table 1: Density and chemical composition of particles from LDWR and other wood species

Residues	Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	pH	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Source
LDWR	200	4.96	70.14	16.13	7.72	Study
<i>Pinus</i> spp.	500 ^a	4.48	51.13	15.10	27.29	Fiorelli et al. (2014)
<i>Eucalyptus urophylla</i>	510 ^b	---	52.00	19.04	28.60	Megaton et al. (2006)
<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i>	620 ^b	---	51.70	20.50	27.80	Megaton et al. (2006)

^a(Ferro, 2018), ^b(Brito & Barrichello, 1977).

The LDWR particles had higher cellulose content and lower lignin when compared to the waste wood of *Pinus* spp. and *Eucalyptus*. Lignin is a compound present in the cell wall of wood fibers responsible for conferring rigidity to the structure of the plant (Zhang & Hu, 2013), which provides greater resistance to compression and bending. This amorphous polymer is responsible for maintaining the bond between the fibers in the wood structure. Thus, a lower lignin content than those found for wood species used commercially in panel production indicates the need for higher resin content for particle adhesion. A high cellulose content increases the strength of wood while a high lignin content increases its stiffness, improving the mechanical properties of particleboard (Fengel & Wegener, 1984). Regarding pH, the LDWR presented similarity with the value found for commercially used *Pinus* wood, a factor that qualifies it as a potential raw material for panel production since pH does not tend to interfere with resin curing, especially urea-formaldehyde type resin.

It is observed that the bulk density of the LDWR wood (200 kg/m³) classifies it as low density which will lead to a larger volume of particles to reach the target density of the composite wood panel and may imply higher resin contents to ensure proper adhesion of the particles.

Characterization of OSB-LDWR panel

Physical characterization

Table 2 presents the average values obtained in the density profile test: average density, density at 2 mm from the left and right faces, and density in the center of the specimens (panel).

Table 2: Average values for density of the OSB-MRBD panel, the density of external and central layers, and respective coefficients of variation (COV)

DENSITY	AVERAGE (kg/m ³) COV (%)
Medium Density	530 (3.95)
Density at 2mm (left)	555 (3.82)
Density at 2 mm (right)	552 (6.51)
Core Density (center)	560 (4.06)

The OSB-LDWR panel presented an average value for bulk density of 550 kg/m³, obtained from the test recommended by the EN 323 (1993) standard. The average density value obtained by the density profile (530 kg/m³) shows that it is possible to produce engineered panels with a given target density using LDWR. The very low COV values show the homogeneity of the obtained values. Figure 2 shows the curve of the average densities along with the panel thickness.

Figure 2: Bulk density profile along with the panel thickness
Source: Own author.

It can be noted the tendency of uniformity of the values along the thickness given by the density profile without the presence of more pronounced peaks. Surdi et al. (2014) obtained density profiles for OSB of Pinus spp. wood with higher density values on the faces and lower in the core, forming a typical profile for "M" shaped wood panels (Tomazello Filho et al., 2010; Rautkari; Kamke; Hughes, 2011). However, the uniformity in the values obtained for the OSB-LDWR panel may be related to the characteristics of the particles and a high compaction ratio of the panel (greater than 2.0) that tend to produce more homogeneous density profiles (Gonçalves et al., 2018).

Table 3 presents the average value of the thermal conductivity of the OSB-LDWR panel and indicative values of the NBR 15220-2 (2005) standard for wood particleboard.

Table 3: Average thermal conductivity (TC) value obtained for the OSB-LDWR panel and values indicated by NBR 15220-2 (2005) standard

Panel		TC (W/mK) (COV)
OSB-LDWR Panel		0.146 (0.79)
Wood Particleboard (NBR 15220:2005)	550 – 650 kg/m ³	0.140
	650 – 750 kg/m ³	0.170

The thermal conductivity of the panel studied attended the recommendation of NBR 15220-2 (2005) which establishes a thermal conductivity between 0.14-0.17 W/mK for medium density wood particleboards, indicating that the material under study presents the potential for applications as a thermal insulator. This property of resistance to heat flow is related to the number of voids (porosity) that exist within the material. The air inside the voids presents very low thermal conductivity, reducing the heat transfer rate inside the panel, which in turn absorbs and scatters radiation (AL-HOMOUD, 2005). For Wang (1988) materials that present thermal conductivity lower than 0.25 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ are considered thermal insulators.

CONCLUSION

The LDWR presented chemical and physical characteristics that qualify it as a raw material for the production of wood-based composite panels, however with the need to use a higher content of the resin than that used to conform panels with Pinus and Eucalyptus wood due to the low density of the wood and little lignin content.

The pressing load used (3.0 MPa) proved sufficient for effective panel compaction as the density profile showed a tendency towards uniformity in the density values throughout the panel thickness with average values close to those obtained by the conventional bulk density measurement test. The thermal conductivity value of the panel is within the conditions required by the NBR 15220-2:2005 standard and the material can be considered a thermal insulator.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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